

Case Report

Unusual Appendiceal Bleeding Revealed on the Third Colonoscopy

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Abstract

Appendiceal bleeding is unusual at all lower gastrointestinal bleeding. We report a clinical case in which emergency appendectomy was performed laparoscopically, an appendiceal diverticulum was observed, and appendiceal diverticular bleeding was suspected.

Clinical Observation

An 80-year-old Japanese female patient was transferred to our emergency hospital on May 2023 with hematochezia. Abdominal computed tomography revealed multiple colonic diverticula on the ascending colon and sigmoid colon, and colonic diverticula hemorrhage was suspected. The following day, colonoscopy was performed, but did not reveal colonic diverticula bleeding. Two days later, the patient experienced two bleeding episodes, and the second colonoscopy was performed; however, no bleeding source was identified. Four days later, three bleeding episodes occurred, and the third colonoscopy was performed, which revealed bleeding from an orifice of an appendix. Emergent laparoscopic surgery was performed, revealing a blood clot at the serosa of the appendix. Macroscopically, the appendix appeared normal, filled with coagulations, however, a small diverticulum with a diameter of 2mm was found in the mucosa of the resected specimen. Histopathological examination showed no inflammatory cell infiltration in the appendix. Malignancy was not identified in the mucosa of the resected specimen. Obvious bleeding source can not be identified. Arteries were found

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near the appendiceal diverticulum, and these were determined to be the likely the cause of the diverticulum bleeding.

Conclusion

This case highlights the need for detailed observation of the orifice of the appendix for acute LGIB. Appendiceal bleeding must be distinguished from LGIB, and surgical resection must be performed as soon as possible. Endoscopists should carefully observe the orifice of the appendix for acute LGIB.

Keywords: Appendiceal Bleeding; Appendiceal Diverticulum; Emergency Appendectomy; Lower Gastrointestinal Bleeding

Introduction

Lower gastrointestinal bleeding (LGIB) can be caused by colonic diverticular bleeding, ischemic colitis, tumors, hemorrhoids, inflammatory bowel disease, and angiodysplasia; however, appendiceal bleeding is very unusual, accounting for approximately 0.4% of all LGIB cases [1]. Herein, we report a case of emergency appendectomy performed in a patient diagnosed with appendiceal bleeding on third-time colonoscopy.

Case Report

An 80-year-old Japanese female patient was transferred to our emergency hospital on May 2023 with hematochezia. She had a body mass index of 21.6kg/m², body temperature of 36.4°C, blood pressure of 123/68mmHg, pulse of 81/min, and oxygen saturation of 98%. Her past history included congestive biliary dilatation, left breast cancer, and irritable bowel syndrome. Physical examination revealed no lower abdominal tenderness on palpation. She had a red blood cell count of 3.40×10⁶ /μL, hemoglobin of 10.8 g/dL, white blood cell count of 4,490/μL, and C-reactive protein of 0.15 mg/dL.

Abdominal computed tomography revealed multiple colonic diverticula on the ascending colon and sigmoid colon, and colonic diverticula hemorrhage was suspected. The following day, colonoscopy was performed, but did not reveal colonic diverticula bleeding. Two days later, the patient experienced two bleeding episodes, and the second colonoscopy was performed; however, no bleeding source was identified. Four days later, three bleeding episodes occurred, and the third colonoscopy was performed, which revealed bleeding from an orifice of an appendix (Figure 1).

Figure 1: A colonoscopy revealing bleeding from the orifice of the appendix (white arrows).

Emergent laparoscopic surgery was performed, revealing a blood clot at the serosa of the appendix (Figure 2).

Figure 2: Emergent laparoscopic surgery was performed, and a blood clot was found at the serosa of an appendix (white arrow).

The operative time was 45 min, and blood loss was minimal. Macroscopically, the appendix appeared normal, measuring 75×14 mm, filled with coagulations (Figure 3); however, a small diverticulum with a diameter of 2mm was found in the mucosa of the resected specimen (Figure 4).

Figure 3: Macroscopically, the appendix appeared normal, measuring 75 × 14 mm filled with coagulations (white arrow).

Figure 4: A small diverticulum with a diameter of 2 mm was detected in the mucosa of the resected specimen (white arrow).

Histopathological examination revealed a pseudodiverticulum that did not involve the muscular layer, and showed no inflammatory cell infiltration in the appendix. Malignancy was not identified in the mucosa of the resected specimen. Obvious bleeding source can not be identified. Arteries were found near the appendiceal diverticulum, and these were determined to be the likely the cause of the diverticulum bleeding (Figure 5). The patient was discharged on postoperative days 8, and remains well without hematochezia 3 years after surgery.

Figure 5: Histopathologically, a pseudodiverticulum was diagnosed without involving the muscular layer (black arrows); however, no obvious bleeding source can be identified (left figure, hematoxylin and eosin staining ×50). Arteries were found near the appendiceal diverticulum (black arrows), and these were determined to be the likely cause of the diverticulum bleeding (right figure, hematoxylin and eosin staining ×100).

Discussion

LGIB has many causes, such as tumors, inflammatory bowel disease, infectious bowel disease, ischemic enteritis, hemorrhoids, and vascular dysplasia. However, bleeding from the appendix is extremely rare, accounting for 0.4% of LGIB cases [1]. Causes include diverticulitis [2], diverticulum [3], acute appendicitis [4,5], endometriosis [6], angiodysplasia [7,8], Crohn's disease [9,10], aortoappendiceal fistula [11], intussusceptions [12], Henoch-Schönlein purpura [13,14], and gastrointestinal stromal tumors [15]. Appendix diverticulum was first described by Kelynack in 1893, who reported that diverticula accounted for 1.74% of appendectomy cases [16].

Appendix diverticula are classified into true diverticula, which involve the entire thickness of the appendix, and pseudodiverticula, which does not involve the muscular layer. True diverticula are associated with appendix bifurcation, ductal deformation, and adhesions.

Although they occur congenitally, the exact cause remains unknown. Pseudodiverticula are thought to develop postnatally due to increased intra-appendicular pressure and account for >95% of all diverticula cases [17]. Our case involved a pseudodiverticulum. Therefore, appendiceal diverticulitis carries a high risk of perforation and often occurs in complicated appendicitis.

Appendiceal bleeding can be diagnosed using colonoscopy, contrast-enhanced abdominal CT, and angiography [7,18,19]. In the present case, the third colonoscopy revealed active bleeding from the appendiceal orifice. Such patients must undergo emergent colonoscopy for acute gastrointestinal bleeding, at least to the terminal ileum. In addition, the orifice of the appendix should be carefully observed. Contrast-enhanced abdominal CT is useful in evaluating diverticulum, neoplasm, or acute inflammation. Although mesenteric artery angiography requires bleeding of >0.5mL/min, vessel embolization is feasible in controlling acute bleeding [7].

Surgical appendectomy is the primary treatment. Other options include endoscopic clipping and interventional radiological arterial embolization. However, because clips occlude the appendiceal orifice, two rebleeding cases required emergency surgery [20,21]. Despite achieving hemostasis with a clip, appendicitis or perforation may occur because of the obstruction of the appendiceal orifice. Although interventional radiological arterial embolization is also a treatment option, rebleeding has been reported, and it is not the first-line treatment [7]. Therefore, surgical appendectomy is the primary treatment for appendiceal bleeding.

Conclusion

Here, we present a case of emergent laparoscopic appendectomy for appendiceal bleeding. Endoscopists should carefully observe the orifice of the appendix for acute LGIB. Appendiceal bleeding must be distinguished from LGIB, and surgical resection must be performed as soon as possible.

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